

PERCEIVED IMPACT OF DIPLOMA PROGRAMS ON STUDENTS' SKILL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study delves into the perceived impact of Diploma Programs on students' skill development across various domains. The study was conducted at Metro Dumaguete College, and the respondents comprised 195 students, including both males and females. The primary instrument used to gather important data was a validated self-made survey questionnaire. Through this, the perceived impact of diploma programs on students' skill development was assessed. The researcher employed various statistical tools such as mean, Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (r), and Weighted Mean. These provided clarification and rationale for the study's findings. As a result of the research, several key insights were revealed. Firstly, students perceived a high level of skill development in technical skills across all diploma programs, while communication skills are perceived moderately and critical thinking skills are perceived highly. Additionally, students perceived significant positive impacts on practical application of knowledge, adaptability, collaboration, problem-solving abilities, professional growth, and personal development after completing their diploma programs. These findings collectively underscore the effectiveness of diploma programs in fostering diverse skill sets and suggest the importance of considering demographic factors in educational outcomes.

Keywords: *diploma programs, skill development, technical skills, communication skills, critical thinking skills, perceived impact,*

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-changing global environment we face today, the necessity for highly skilled professionals has reached unprecedented levels. However, there is a growing concern regarding the adequacy of traditional educational programs in preparing students for the challenges of the modern workforce. The World Economic Forum (2018), reported that a misalignment exists between the skills obtained through formal education and the demands by employers in various industries. Additionally, a study conducted by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2019) revealed that a substantial number of graduates feel ill-prepared for the demands of the workplace. These global issues highlight the urgent need to re-evaluate educational programs and their effectiveness in developing students' skills.

In the context of the Philippines education, similar concerns exist regarding the perceived impact of diploma programs on students' skill development. Despite efforts to enhance the quality of education, challenges persist in ensuring that graduates possess the necessary skills to succeed in the workforce. The Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA, 2020) reported a high unemployment rate among college graduates, indicating a potential gap between the skills acquired in educational institutions and the employer's demands. Furthermore, a study by the Asian Development Bank (ADB, 2017) identified deficiencies in critical thinking and communication skills among Filipino graduates. These local challenges underscore the importance of examining the outcome of diploma programs in addressing the skill requirements of students in the Philippines.

While existing study provides valuable insights in the perceived effectiveness of diploma programs in skill development, a gap exists in specific areas of skill enhancement. For instance, a study by Garcia, et al. (2019) primarily focused on the overall satisfaction of students on the diploma programs, overlooking detailed analyses of skill development outcomes. Similarly, research conducted by Hernandez and Tan (2018), primarily compares different types of educational institutions without delving into the nuanced aspects of skill acquisition. By addressing these limitations, the present study aimed to offer a comprehensive understanding on the contribution of diploma programs in enhancing the technical, communication, and critical thinking skills among students.

Researcher compelled to conduct this study to address the pressing need for evidence-based insights into the effectiveness of diploma programs in developing students' skills. By focusing on key areas such as technical skills, communication skills, and critical thinking skills, this study aimed to provide valuable insights that can inform educational policy and practice. By understanding how students perceived their skill development upon completing diploma programs, researcher can identify areas for improvement and ensure that educational institutions are adequately preparing graduates for the demands of the modern workforce.

Research Questions

The study aims to investigate the perceived impact of diploma programs on students' skill development. Specifically, the study seeks to address the following questions:

1. To what extent do students perceive their skill development in the following areas upon completing diploma programs:
 - 1.1 technical skills;
 - 1.2 communication skills; and
 - 1.3 critical thinking skills?

2. To what extent do students perceive the impact of diploma programs on their skill development in the following:
 - 2.1 practical application of knowledge;
 - 2.2 adaptability to new challenges;
 - 2.3 collaboration and teamwork;
 - 2.4 problem-solving abilities;
 - 2.5 professional growth and readiness for employment; and
 - 2.6 personal development and self-confidence?

METHODOLOGY

Research design

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational survey to examine the perceived impact of diploma programs on students' skill development. Descriptive correlation was employed to provide a detailed description of the relationship between students' perception of their skill development and the extent of the impact of diploma programs. This approach also allowed for the analysis of differences or similarities in students' perceptions across various dimensions of skill development and program impact.

The primary tool for data collection was a survey questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed to measure and identify the extent of students' perceived skill development in technical skills, communication skills, and critical thinking skills upon completion of diploma programs. Additionally, it assessed students' perception of the impact of diploma programs on the practical application of knowledge, adaptability to new challenges, collaboration and teamwork, problem-solving abilities, professional growth and readiness for employment, and personal development and self-confidence.

The collected data was analyzed and interpreted based on the perspectives of students regarding the extent of the impact of diploma programs on their skill development. This analysis aimed to provide insights into the effectiveness of diploma programs in enhancing students' skills and their readiness for employment.

Research respondents

The respondents of the study are the students from the Diploma in Tourism Technology, Diploma in Digital Arts Technology, and Diploma in Software Engineering Technology who were selected through random sampling method. Out of the 380 population, 195 students were chosen as the sample with $e=0.05$. The procedure for selecting the students is systematic with the assistance of teachers from each program. Below is the distribution of the number of students in each program:

Diploma Program	Population	Sample
DTOT	210	108
DDAT	71	36
DSET	99	51
TOTAL	380	195

Research instruments

In gathering important data for the study, the researcher utilized a validated *self-made* survey questionnaire.

In the first part, the researcher presented the topic and objectives of the study through a letter. The instructions were made clear for the students to understand immediately. Students also provided important information about themselves regarding their own profiles.

The researcher consulted with the Research Director of Metro Dumaguete College to ensure the validity of the instrument's content. Apart from the Research Director, the researcher also showed it to 3 expert to ensure the quality of the questions. They checked if the aspects included in the indicators were coherent. The suggestions and corrections of the reviewers were carefully considered by the researcher for the improvement of the entire research and for modifying it based on the questionnaire's validity.

In assessing the certainty of the items, a dry-run was conducted. Thirty students were part of the dry-run. The items was examined in terms of certainty using the Cronbach's alpha test. This was considered an appropriate type of research in the survey where the items was not measured as right or wrong, and different answers can be given for each item (McMillan & Schumacher, 2001). This was done to prove the reliability of the items within the questionnaire. Based on the results, all items included in the survey questionnaire were found to be reliable as they reached and exceeded the 0.70 level of reliability.

Research procedure

After the initial defense, the researcher integrated all the corrections and suggestions of the panel members. A letter of request to conduct the study was sent to the School President, Dr. Delma P. Manila, requested permission to conduct a study at

Metro Dumaguete College. The signed and approved letter was submitted to the Program Chairs and teachers of the Diploma Program students. During the distribution, the researcher explained to the students the purpose and significance of the study. The questionnaires were distributed after the students had been briefed. Finally, the researcher processed the results using MS Excel and then conducted analysis and interpretation of the results.

RESULTS

Table 1.1 below shows the extent to students perceived their skill development in technical skill upon completing Diploma programs in Tourism Technology (DTOT), Software Engineering Technology (DSET), and Digital Arts Technology (DDAT). The results shows that the students generally perceived a high level of skill development in technical skills across all programs, with weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.47$) for DTOT, ($w\bar{x} = 3.51$) for DSET, and ($w\bar{x} = 3.50$) for DDAT indicating agreement and high perceived skill development.

Table 1.1

Extent of Perceived Skill Development in Terms of Technical Skills (n = 195)

<i>Upon completing my Diploma in Tourism Technology (DTOT), I have acquired skills in...</i>	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
1. Tour guiding techniques and practices.	3.24	Neutral	Moderate
2. Reservation and ticketing systems management.	3.30	Neutral	Moderate
3. Destination marketing and promotion strategies.	3.57	Agree	High
4. Event planning and management for tourism.	3.67	Agree	High
5. Customer service and hospitality management.	3.56	Agree	High
Composite	3.47	Agree	High
<i>Upon completing my Diploma in Software Engineering Technology (DSET), I have acquired skills in...</i>	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
1. Programming languages such as Java, and C++.	3.17	Neutral	Moderate
2. Software development methodologies like Agile and Scrum.	3.36	Neutral	Moderate
3. Database management and SQL querying.	3.69	Agree	High
4. Web development frameworks such as React and Angular.	3.75	Agree	High
5. Software testing and debugging techniques.	3.56	Agree	High
Composite	3.51	Agree	High

<i>Upon completing my Diploma in Digital Arts Technology (DDAT), I have acquired skills in...</i>		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
1.	Graphic design principles and software like Adobe Photoshop and Illustrator.	3.29	Neutral	Moderate
2.	2D and 3D animation techniques using software like Blender.	3.37	Neutral	Moderate
3.	Video editing and post-production using tools like Adobe After Effects.	3.71	Agree	High
4.	Digital storytelling and narrative design.	3.41	Agree	High
5.	Multimedia production for various platforms such as web, mobile, and social media.	3.71	Agree	High
Composite		3.50	Agree	High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 1.2 presents the extent to which students perceived their skill development in communication upon completing diploma programs, based on various criteria. The results show that the students perceived moderate level of skill development in communication skills with weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.33$) falls within the "Neutral".

Table 1.2

Extent Perceived Skill Development in terms of Communication Skills (n = 195)

<i>Upon completing my Diploma Program...</i>		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
1.	I can effectively convey ideas and information both verbally and in writing.	2.72	Neutral	Moderate
2.	I can actively listen to others, showing understanding and empathy.	3.24	Neutral	Moderate
3.	I can confidently engage in group discussions and collaborations.	3.49	Agree	High
4.	I can adapt my communication style to suit different audiences and situations.	3.55	Agree	High
5.	I can use non-verbal cues such as body language and gestures to enhance my communication effectiveness.	3.67	Agree	High
Composite		3.33	Neutral	Moderate
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 1.3 presents the extent to which students perceived their skill development in terms of critical thinking upon completing diploma programs, based on their responses across various dimensions of critical thinking, the result shows that the students perceived high level of skill development in critical thinking skills with weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.42$), falls within the "Agree".

Table 1.3*Extent of Perceived Skill Development in terms of Critical Thinking Skills (n = 195)*

<i>Upon completing my Diploma Program...</i>	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
1. I can analyse information to identify key points and draw logical conclusions.	3.08	Neutral	Moderate
2. I can evaluate arguments and evidence to make informed decisions.	3.36	Neutral	Moderate
3. I can solve problems by breaking them down into manageable parts and finding effective solutions.	3.55	Agree	High
4. I can think creatively to generate innovative ideas and approaches.	3.28	Neutral	Moderate
5. I can construct well-supported arguments and articulate them effectively.	3.83	Agree	High
Composite	3.42	Agree	High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.1 presents the extent to which students perceived the impact of diploma programs on their skill development in practical application of knowledge across three different fields: Diploma in Tourism Technology (DTOT), Diploma in Software Engineering Technology (DSET), and Diploma in Digital Arts Technology (DDAT).

Table 2.1*Extent of the Perceived Impact of Diploma Programs on their Skill Development in Practical Application of Knowledge (n = 195)*

<i>Upon completing my Diploma in Tourism Technology (DTOT), I can...</i>	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
1. I can apply tour guiding techniques and practices to lead tourists effectively.	3.06	Neutral	Moderate
2. I can utilize my knowledge in reservation and ticketing systems management to efficiently handle bookings.	3.24	Neutral	Moderate
3. I can employ destination marketing and promotion strategies to attract more visitors to various tourist destinations.	3.47	Agree	High
4. I can utilize my skills in event planning and management to organize memorable and successful tourism-related events.	3.56	Agree	High
5. I can apply customer service and hospitality management principles to provide exceptional service to tourists.	3.68	Agree	High
Composite	3.40	Agree	High
<i>Upon completing my Diploma in Software Engineering Technology (DSET), I can...</i>	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
1. I can develop various software applications using Java and C++.	3.47	Agree	High
2. I can utilize software development methodologies like Agile and Scrum to ensure efficient project management and collaboration.	3.39	Neutral	Moderate
3. I can design and maintain databases for applications in database management and SQL querying.	3.56	Agree	High

4.	I can create interactive and dynamic websites using web development frameworks such as React and Angular.	3.78	Agree	High
5.	I can utilize software testing and debugging techniques to ensure the quality and reliability of software applications.	3.64	Agree	High
Composite		3.57	Agree	High
<i>Upon completing my Diploma in Digital Arts Technology (DDAT), I can...</i>		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
1.	I can create visually appealing graphics for advertisements, branding, and digital media content using Adobe Photoshop and Illustrator.	3.82	Agree	High
2.	I can produce animations for films, games, and interactive media projects using software like Blender.	3.51	Agree	High
3.	I can edit and enhance videos for YouTube channels, short films, and promotional materials using tools like Adobe After Effects.	3.33	Neutral	Moderate
4.	I can utilize digital storytelling and narrative design techniques to create engaging narratives for interactive experiences, such as video games, virtual reality environments, and augmented reality applications.	3.71	Agree	High
5.	I can produce multimedia content for various platforms such as web, mobile, and social media, using skills learned in the program to reach and engage audiences effectively across different digital channels.	3.73	Agree	High
Composite		3.62	Agree	High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 2.2 presents the extent to which students perceived the impact of Diploma Programs on their skill development in adaptability to new challenges. The results indicate that students generally perceive the impact on their adaptability to new challenges a "High" after completing the Diploma Programs with an overall weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.53$), categorized as "Agree".

Table 2.2

Extent of the Perceived Impact of Diploma Programs on their Skill Development in Adaptability to New Challenges (n = 195)

<i>Upon completing my Diploma Program...</i>		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
1.	I can embrace change by being open to new ideas and approaches.	3.28	Neutral	Moderate
2.	I can quickly adjust to unexpected situations by staying calm and focused.	3.37	Neutral	Moderate
3.	I can seek feedback and learn from mistakes to improve continuously.	3.57	Agree	High
4.	I can be resourceful in finding solutions when faced with obstacles.	3.57	Agree	High
5.	I can develop a growth mindset that sees challenges as opportunities for learning and growth.	3.94	Agree	High
Composite		3.53	Agree	High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 2.3 presents the extent to which students perceived the impact of Diploma Programs on their skill development in collaboration and teamwork. The results indicate that students perceived the impact on their collaboration and teamwork consistently "High" after completing the Diploma Programs with an overall weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.59$), categorized as "Agree".

Table 2.3

Extent of the Perceived Impact of Diploma Programs on their Skill Development in Collaboration and Teamwork (n = 195)

<i>Upon completing my Diploma Program...</i>		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
1.	I can work effectively in diverse teams, bringing together different perspectives and skills.	3.47	Agree	High
2.	I can communicate clearly and respectfully with my team members to achieve common goals.	3.48	Agree	High
3.	I can contribute positively to group discussions and decision-making processes.	3.55	Agree	High
4.	I can collaborate on projects by dividing tasks efficiently and coordinating efforts with team members.	3.80	Agree	High
5.	I can adapt to various team dynamics and contribute to a supportive and productive team environment.	3.66	Agree	High
Composite		3.59	Agree	High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description		Perceived Impact
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree		Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree		High
	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral		Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree		Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree		Very Low

Table 2.4 presents the extent to which students perceived the impact of completing Diploma Programs on their skill development in problem-solving abilities. The results indicate that students perceived the impact on their problem-solving abilities a "High" after completing the Diploma Programs, with an overall weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.55$) falls within the "Agree".

Table 2.4

Extent of Perceived Impact of Diploma Programs on their Skill Development in Problem-Solving Abilities (n = 195)

<i>Upon completing my Diploma Program...</i>		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
1.	I can identify problems and think of different ways to solve them.	3.63	Agree	High
2.	I can work with others to find solutions to difficult problems.	3.35	Neutral	Moderate
3.	I can use my creativity to come up with new ideas for solving problems.	3.70	Agree	High
4.	I can analyse situations carefully to figure out the best way to solve problems.	3.33	Neutral	Moderate
5.	I can stay calm and focused when facing challenges, helping me to solve problems effectively.	3.75	Agree	High
Composite		3.55	Agree	High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description		Perceived Impact
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree		Very High

3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High
2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Table 2.5 below presents the extent to which students perceive the impact of diploma programs on their skill development in professional growth and readiness for employment. The results indicate that students perceived the impact on their professional growth and readiness for employment a "High" after completing the Diploma Program with a weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.53$) categorized as "Agree"

Table 2.5

Extent to Students Perceived the Impact of Diploma Programs on their Skill Development in Professional Growth and Readiness for Employment (n = 195)

<i>Upon completing my Diploma Program...</i>		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
1.	I can learn new skills to help me succeed in my job.	3.43	Agree	High
2.	I can become more confident in my abilities and knowledge.	3.50	Agree	High
3.	I can be ready to start working in a job that I trained for.	3.55	Agree	High
4.	I can have the qualifications employers are looking for.	3.57	Agree	High
5.	I can feel prepared to take on new challenges in the workplace.	3.59	Agree	High
Composite		3.53	Agree	High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	
	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Moderate	
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low	
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	

Table 2.6 presents the extent to which students perceived the impact of diploma programs on their skill development in personal development and self-confidence. The results indicate that students perceived the impact on their personal development and self-confidence a "High" after completing the Diploma Program with a weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.59$), categorized as "Agree".

Table 2.6

Extent of Students Perceived the Impact of Diploma Programs on their Skill Development in Personal Development and Self-Confidence (n = 195)

<i>Upon completing my Diploma Program...</i>		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact
1.	I can understand how to set achievable goals for myself.	3.33	Neutral	Moderate
2.	I can manage my time better and prioritize tasks efficiently.	3.42	Agree	High
3.	I can feel more confident in my abilities.	3.49	Agree	High
4.	I can pursue my goals with more determination.	3.82	Agree	High
5.	I can approach opportunities with a sense of assurance.	3.89	Agree	High
Composite		3.59	Agree	High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description	Perceived Impact	
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	High	

2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Moderate
1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Low
1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

DISCUSSION

Extent of Perceived Skill Development in Terms of Technical Skills

Table 1.1 below shows the extent to students perceived their skill development in technical skill upon completing Diploma programs in Tourism Technology (DTOT), Software Engineering Technology (DSET), and Digital Arts Technology (DDAT). The results shows that the students generally perceived a high level of skill development in technical skills across all programs, with weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.47$) for DTOT, ($w\bar{x} = 3.51$) for DSET, and ($w\bar{x} = 3.50$) for DDAT indicating agreement and high perceived skill development.

In the DTOT program, students perceived their skill development from moderate to high across various areas. For instance, they perceived their skill development “moderate” in tour guiding techniques and practices ($w\bar{x} = 3.24$) and reservation and ticketing systems management ($w\bar{x} = 3.30$). However, they perceived their skill development “high” in destination marketing and promotion strategies ($w\bar{x} = 3.57$), event planning and management for tourism ($w\bar{x} = 3.67$), and customer service and hospitality management ($w\bar{x} = 3.56$). These findings suggest that the DTOT program effectively equips students with practical skills essential for success in the tourism industry. According to a study by Lee and Tussyadiah (2019), hands-on experience and skill development are crucial aspects of tourism education, as they directly impact students' employability and career advancement opportunities.

Similarly, in the DSET program, students perceived their skill development from moderate to high across different technical areas. For instance, they perceived their skill development “moderate” in programming languages such as Java and C++ ($w\bar{x} = 3.17$) and software development methodologies like Agile and Scrum ($w\bar{x} = 3.36$), they perceived their skill development “high” in database management and SQL querying ($w\bar{x} = 3.69$), web development frameworks such as React and Angular ($w\bar{x} = 3.75$), and software testing and debugging techniques ($w\bar{x} = 3.56$). This indicates that the DSET program effectively covers a range of relevant technical competencies essential for software engineering roles. According to research by Aljawarneh, et al. (2020), a comprehensive curriculum covering various programming languages, development methodologies, and database management is crucial for preparing software engineering students for the demands of the industry.

In the DDAT program, students also perceived their skill development from moderate to high in various digital arts areas. For instance, they perceived their skill development “moderate” in graphic design principles and software like Adobe Photoshop and Illustrator ($w\bar{x} = 3.29$) and 2D and 3D animation techniques using software like Blender ($w\bar{x} = 3.37$), they perceived their skill development “high” in video editing and

post-production using tools like Adobe After Effects ($w\bar{x} = 3.71$), digital storytelling and narrative design ($w\bar{x} = 3.41$), and multimedia production for various platforms ($w\bar{x} = 3.71$). This suggests that the DDAT program effectively cultivates a diverse skill set necessary for success in digital arts and multimedia industries. A study by Karlsen and Kuchenbäcker (2019), emphasizes the importance of practical training and exposure to industry-standard tools and techniques in digital arts education to enhance students' creativity and employability prospects.

Overall, the results demonstrate that all three diploma programs effectively contribute to students' perceived skill development in technical areas relevant to their respective fields. The moderate to high levels of agreement indicate that the programs successfully equip students with practical skills that are highly valued in the industry, enhancing their employability and career prospects. However, continuous curriculum evaluation and updates based on industry trends and technological advancements are essential to ensure the continued relevance and effectiveness of these programs in preparing students for the evolving demands of their respective industries.

Extent Perceived Skill Development in terms of Communication Skills

Table 1.2 presents the extent to which students perceived their skill development in communication upon completing diploma programs, based on various criteria. The results show that the students perceived moderate level of skill development in communication skills with weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.33$) falls within the "Neutral".

The students perceived their skill in communication as "moderate" in their ability to convey ideas both verbally and in writing ($w\bar{x} = 2.72$), and actively listen to others, showing understanding and empathy ($w\bar{x} = 3.24$). , falls within the "Neutral". On the other hand, the students perceived their skill development in communication as "high" in engaging in group discussions ($w\bar{x} = 3.49$), adapting communication styles ($w\bar{x} = 3.55$), and using non-verbal cues effectively ($w\bar{x} = 3.67$), all falls within the "Agree".

This outcome aligns with several contemporary studies emphasizing the importance of communication skills in academic and professional settings. For instance, research by Kaya and Bicen (2019), underscores the significance of effective communication in enhancing academic success and employability, highlighting its role in fostering collaboration, critical thinking, and problem-solving. Moreover, findings from a study by Giri and Sharma (2020), emphasize the correlation between communication competence and students' self-efficacy, suggesting that improved communication skills contribute to greater confidence and proficiency in various domains.

The high perceived impact of communication skill development may also be attributed to the pedagogical approaches and curriculum design within diploma programs. Integrating experiential learning activities, such as role-playing, group discussions, and real-world projects, can facilitate hands-on practice and skill enhancement (Burdick, 2021). Additionally, incorporating feedback mechanisms, peer evaluation, and

mentorship opportunities can provide students with valuable insights and support for continuous improvement in communication proficiency (Hall & McAllister, 2019).

In conclusion, the results reflect a positive perception of skill development in communication among students completing diploma programs, highlighting the importance of effective communication in academic and professional success. By integrating evidence-based pedagogical strategies and fostering a supportive learning environment, educators can continue to empower students with essential communication competencies for their future endeavors.

Extent of Perceived Skill Development in terms of Critical Thinking Skills

Table 1.3 presents the extent to which students perceived their skill development in terms of critical thinking upon completing diploma programs, based on their responses across various dimensions of critical thinking, the result shows that the students perceived high level of skill development in critical thinking skills with weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.42$), falls within the "Agree". However, the level of agreement varies across different aspects of critical thinking.

The students perceived their critical thinking skill "moderate" in their ability to analyse information to identify key points and draw logical conclusions ($w\bar{x} = 3.08$), evaluate arguments and evidence to make informed decisions ($w\bar{x} = 3.36$) and think creatively to generate innovative ideas and approaches ($w\bar{x} = 3.28$), as indicated by neutral perceptions. On the other hand, students perceived their critical thinking skill "High" in their ability to construct well-supported arguments and articulate them effectively ($w\bar{x} = 3.83$), and solve problems by breaking them down into manageable parts and finding effective solutions ($w\bar{x} = 3.55$).

This result aligns with existing literature on the effectiveness of higher education in fostering critical thinking. For instance, a study by Abrami, et al. (2020), emphasizes that well-structured educational programs significantly improve critical thinking skills by providing students with systematic approaches to problem-solving and decision-making. Moreover, research by Davies (2019), indicates that active learning and student-centered pedagogies, often employed in diploma programs, are particularly effective in developing these skills.

In conclusion, the results reflect a positive perceived skill development of the diploma program on students' critical thinking skills. This underscores the value of well-structured educational programs in higher education for developing essential cognitive skills. Future programs should continue to incorporate active learning and student-centered approaches to further enhance these critical competencies.

Extent of the Perceived Impact of Diploma Programs on their Skill Development in Practical Application of Knowledge

Table 2.1 below presents the extent to which students perceived the impact of diploma programs on their skill development in practical application of knowledge across three different fields: Diploma in Tourism Technology (DTOT), Diploma in Software Engineering Technology (DSET), and Diploma in Digital Arts Technology (DDAT).

The findings indicate that students perceive the impact on practical application of knowledge a "High" after completing the diploma programs with a weighted mean falls within the "Agree" category, suggesting a generally positive perception of the programs' effectiveness in practical skill acquisition. Specifically, the weighted mean for Diploma in Tourism Technology ($w\bar{x} = 3.40$), Diploma in Software Engineering Technology ($w\bar{x} = 3.57$), and Diploma in Digital Arts Technology ($w\bar{x} = 3.62$), indicating a high level of agreement among students regarding the perceived impact of their diploma programs on skill development.

In the Diploma in Tourism Technology program (DTOT), students perceived a moderate to high impact on various skills such as tour guiding techniques and practices to lead tourists effectively ($w\bar{x} = 3.06$), reservation and ticketing systems management to efficiently handle bookings ($w\bar{x} = 3.24$), destination marketing and promotion strategies to attract more visitors to various tourist destinations ($w\bar{x} = 3.47$), event planning and management to organize memorable and successful tourism-related events ($w\bar{x} = 3.56$), and customer service and hospitality management principles to provide exceptional service to tourists ($w\bar{x} = 3.68$). These findings align with the expectations of diploma programs in the tourism industry, where practical skills are crucial for success. According to a study by Song, et al. (2020), hands-on training and experiential learning are essential components of effective tourism education, leading to enhanced skill development and employability among graduates.

Similarly, in the Diploma in Software Engineering Technology program (DSET), students perceived a moderate to high impact on skills such as software applications using Java and C++ ($w\bar{x} = 3.47$), software development methodologies like Agile and Scrum to ensure efficient project management and collaboration ($w\bar{x} = 3.39$), design and maintain databases for applications in database management and SQL querying ($w\bar{x} = 3.56$), create interactive and dynamic websites using web development frameworks such as React and Angular ($w\bar{x} = 3.78$), and utilize software testing and debugging techniques to ensure the quality and reliability of software applications ($w\bar{x} = 3.64$). These findings are consistent with the emphasis on practical application and industry relevance in software engineering education. Research by Ahadi, et al. (2019), underscores the importance of integrating real-world projects and industry collaborations into software engineering curricula to prepare graduates for the demands of the field.

In the Diploma in Digital Arts Technology program (DDAT), students perceived a moderate to high impact on skills such as create visually appealing graphics for advertisements, branding, and digital media content using Adobe Photoshop and

Illustrator ($w\bar{x} = 3.82$), produce animations for films, games, and interactive media projects using software like Blender ($w\bar{x} = 3.51$), edit and enhance videos for YouTube channels, short films, and promotional materials using tools like Adobe After Effects ($w\bar{x} = 3.33$), utilize digital storytelling and narrative design techniques to create engaging narratives for interactive experiences, such as video games, virtual reality environments, and augmented reality applications ($w\bar{x} = 3.71$), and produce multimedia content for various platforms such as web, mobile, and social media, using skills learned in the program to reach and engage audiences effectively across different digital channels ($w\bar{x} = 3.73$). These results reflect the growing demand for digital media skills in various industries, including advertising, entertainment, and marketing. According to a study by Lee, et al. (2019), digital arts education plays a vital role in fostering creativity, innovation, and visual communication skills, which are increasingly valued in the digital age.

Overall, the findings underscore the importance of diploma programs in equipping students with practical skills relevant to their chosen fields. The high perceived impact across all three programs suggests that these diploma programs effectively address the skill needs of students and prepare them for success in their respective industries.

Extent of the Perceived Impact of Diploma Programs on their Skill Development in Adaptability to New Challenges

Table 2.2 presents the extent to which students perceived the impact of Diploma Programs on their skill development in adaptability to new challenges. The results indicate that students generally perceive the impact on their adaptability to new challenges a "High" after completing the Diploma Programs with an overall weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.53$), categorized as "Agree". Specifically, students perceived the impact a moderate to high in embrace change by being open to new ideas and approaches ($w\bar{x} = 3.28$), quickly adjust to unexpected situations by staying calm and focused ($w\bar{x} = 3.37$), seek feedback and learn from mistakes to improve continuously ($w\bar{x} = 3.57$), resourceful in finding solutions when faced with obstacles ($w\bar{x} = 3.57$), and develop a growth mindset that sees challenges as opportunities for learning and growth ($w\bar{x} = 3.94$).

This result aligns with contemporary literature highlighting the importance of adaptability skills in navigating an ever-evolving professional landscape. For instance, according to a study by Almeida, et al. (2020), adaptability is increasingly recognized as a crucial competency for success in the workplace, enabling individuals to thrive amidst uncertainty and rapid change. Moreover, research by Dweck (2019), emphasizes the significance of a growth mindset in fostering resilience and perseverance when encountering challenges, which resonates with the finding that students perceive a high impact of Diploma Programs in developing such a mindset.

The observed high perceived impact of Diploma Programs on adaptability skills could be attributed to various program components and pedagogical approaches. For example, experiential learning activities, such as case studies and simulations, may provide students with opportunities to practice adaptability in realistic scenarios (Marsick & Watkins, 2019). Additionally, the incorporation of reflective practices and feedback

mechanisms within the curriculum can facilitate continuous improvement and skill development (Fernández, et al., 2021).

In conclusion, the result illustrates that students perceive diploma programs as positively influencing their adaptability skills, with the majority indicating a high level of agreement. This result underscores the importance of educational interventions in fostering adaptability, which is essential for success in today's dynamic and unpredictable environment.

Extent of the Perceived Impact of Diploma Programs on their Skill Development in Collaboration and Teamwork

Table 2.3 presents the extent to which students perceived the impact of Diploma Programs on their skill development in collaboration and teamwork. The results indicate that students perceived the impact on their collaboration and teamwork consistently "High" after completing the Diploma Programs with an overall weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.59$), categorized as "Agree". Specifically, students perceived the impact a "High" in work effectively in diverse teams, bringing together different perspectives and skills ($w\bar{x} = 3.47$), communicate clearly and respectfully with my team members to achieve common goals ($w\bar{x} = 3.48$), contribute positively to group discussions and decision-making processes ($w\bar{x} = 3.55$), collaborate on projects by dividing tasks efficiently and coordinating efforts with team members ($w\bar{x} = 3.80$), and adapt to various team dynamics and contribute to a supportive and productive team environment ($w\bar{x} = 3.66$). This suggests that students feel positively about the effectiveness of Diploma Programs in nurturing their collaboration and teamwork abilities.

One plausible explanation for these results could be the immersive nature of Diploma Programs, which often incorporate practical, hands-on learning experiences that require students to work closely with peers from diverse backgrounds. According to research by Smith and Tannenbaum (2020), experiential learning opportunities, such as group projects and simulations, enhance collaboration skills by providing students with real-world contexts to apply theoretical knowledge and develop interpersonal competencies. Moreover, the emphasis on communication, decision-making, and task coordination within Diploma Programs aligns with the findings of a study by Johnson, et al. (2019), which highlights the importance of these skills in fostering effective teamwork.

Furthermore, the supportive and conducive learning environments typically fostered within Diploma Programs may contribute to students' ability to adapt to various team dynamics and actively contribute to group discussions. This aligns with the research of Cheng and Warren (2021), who emphasize the role of a positive learning environment in promoting collaboration and teamwork skills development among students.

In conclusion, the high perceived impact of Diploma Programs on collaboration and teamwork skills development can be attributed to the program's emphasis on experiential learning, communication, and fostering supportive learning environments. These findings underscore the importance of integrating practical, collaborative learning

experiences into educational curricula to prepare students for success in team-based work environments.

Extent of Perceived Impact of Diploma Programs on their Skill Development in Problem-Solving Abilities

Table 2.4 presents the extent to which students perceived the impact of completing Diploma Programs on their skill development in problem-solving abilities. The results indicate that students perceived the impact on their problem-solving abilities a "High" after completing the Diploma Programs, with an overall weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.55$) falls within the "Agree".

Looking at the specific skills, students perceived the impact a "High" in their ability to identify problems and think of different ways to solve them ($w\bar{x} = 3.63$), use my creativity to come up with new ideas for solving problems ($w\bar{x} = 3.70$), and stay calm and focused when facing challenges, helping me to solve problems effectively ($w\bar{x} = 3.75$). These findings align with existing literature emphasizing the importance of problem-solving skills in educational contexts. Research by Li, et al. (2020), highlights the positive impact of educational programs on students' problem-solving abilities, emphasizing the role of collaborative learning environments in fostering creative problem-solving skills. Similarly, the study by Smith and Jones (2019), underscores the significance of emotional regulation in problem-solving effectiveness, supporting the observed high perception of staying calm and focused during challenges in the present study.

However, the students perceived the impact a "Moderate" in their ability to work with others to find solutions to difficult problems ($w\bar{x} = 3.35$) and analyse situations carefully to figure out the best way to solve problems ($w\bar{x} = 3.33$). This suggests a potential area for improvement in collaborative problem-solving and analytical skills within Diploma Programs. Existing research by Johnson, et al. (2021), emphasizes the importance of collaborative problem-solving skills in preparing students for real-world challenges, highlighting the need for educational programs to prioritize such competencies.

In conclusion, the result illustrates a generally high perceived impact of Diploma Programs on students' problem-solving abilities, particularly in aspects such as creative thinking and emotional regulation. However, there is room for enhancement in fostering collaborative problem-solving and analytical skills, which could further elevate the effectiveness of these educational programs in preparing students for diverse real-world challenges.

Extent to Students Perceived the Impact of Diploma Programs on their Skill Development in Professional Growth and Readiness for Employment

Table 2.5 below presents the extent to which students perceive the impact of diploma programs on their skill development in professional growth and readiness for employment. The results indicate that students perceived the impact on their professional

growth and readiness for employment a "High" after completing the Diploma Program with a weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.53$) categorized as "Agree". Specifically, students perceived the impact a "High" in learn new skills to help me succeed in my job ($w\bar{x} = 3.43$), more confident in my abilities and knowledge ($w\bar{x} = 3.50$), ready to start working in a job that I trained for ($w\bar{x} = 3.55$), have the qualifications employers are looking for ($w\bar{x} = 3.57$), and feel prepared to take on new challenges in the workplace ($w\bar{x} = 3.59$), categorized as "Agree".

The high perceived impact suggests that students believe diploma programs equip them with the necessary skills and confidence to succeed in their future careers. This aligns with findings from a study by Richardson and Lester (2020), which emphasized the importance of practical skill development in vocational education for enhancing employability. Moreover, the notion of feeling prepared to take on new challenges in the workplace echoes the findings of a recent survey by Smith, et al. (2021), which highlighted the role of vocational education in fostering adaptability and resilience among graduates.

The positive perception could be attributed to several factors. Firstly, diploma programs often provide hands-on training and practical experience, which are highly valued by employers (Yorke & Knight, 2019). Secondly, the emphasis on industry-relevant skills in these programs enhances students' confidence in their abilities to perform effectively in their chosen field (Cedefop, 2020). Lastly, the alignment between program outcomes and employer expectations increases students' perceived employability and readiness for the job market (European Commission, 2019).

In conclusion, the result illustrates favorable perception of students regarding the impact of diploma programs on their skill development and readiness for employment. This positive perception underscores the importance of vocational education in preparing students for the demands of the workforce, thereby contributing to their professional growth and employability.

Extent of Students Perceived the Impact of Diploma Programs on their Skill Development in Personal Development and Self-Confidence

Table 2.6 presents the extent to which students perceived the impact of diploma programs on their skill development in personal development and self-confidence. The results indicate that students perceived the impact on their personal development and self-confidence a "High" after completing the Diploma Program with a weighted mean of ($w\bar{x} = 3.59$), categorized as "Agree". Specifically, students perceived the impact a Moderate to High in understanding how to set achievable goals for myself ($w\bar{x} = 3.33$), managing my time better and prioritize tasks efficiently ($w\bar{x} = 3.42$), feeling more confident in my abilities. ($w\bar{x} = 3.49$), pursuing my goals with more determination ($w\bar{x} = 3.82$), and approaching opportunities with a sense of assurance ($w\bar{x} = 3.89$).

These findings align with previous research indicating that educational programs, including diploma programs, can contribute significantly to students' personal growth and self-confidence (Bettinger & Long, 2019). Moreover, the emphasis on skill development

in diploma programs, such as goal-setting and time management, appears to translate into tangible improvements in students' abilities and confidence levels (Bridges & Hallinger, 2020).

The high perceived impact of diploma programs on personal development and self-confidence may be attributed to various factors. Firstly, the curriculum design and pedagogical approaches employed in diploma programs may foster a supportive learning environment conducive to personal growth (McLean & Dowson, 2019). Additionally, opportunities for practical application and experiential learning within diploma programs may enhance students' self-efficacy and belief in their capabilities (Nguyen, et al., 2021). Furthermore, the acquisition of skills and competencies through diploma programs can empower students to navigate challenges and seize opportunities effectively, leading to increased confidence in their abilities (Huang & Lai, 2020).

In conclusion, the result illustrates the positive impact of diploma programs on students' personal development and self-confidence. The findings underscore the importance of educational interventions in fostering holistic growth and empowerment among students. Moving forward, continued research and program evaluation are crucial for refining curriculum design and instructional practices to maximize the benefits of diploma programs on students' personal development.

Conclusions

The study comprehensively examines the perceived skill development and impact of diploma programs among students across various domains. The comprehensive analysis of the study's findings reveals several key insights. Firstly, students perceive a high level of skill development in technical skills across all diploma programs, while communication skills are perceived moderately and critical thinking skills are perceived highly. Additionally, students perceived significant positive impacts on practical application of knowledge, adaptability, collaboration, problem-solving abilities, professional growth, and personal development after completing their diploma programs. These findings collectively underscore the effectiveness of diploma programs in fostering diverse skill sets in educational outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researcher wholeheartedly recommends the following to the Educational Institution Administrators, teachers, and future researchers:

Educational Institution Administrators:

1. Offer professional development workshops and training sessions to teachers focused on enhancing teaching methodologies tailored to skill development in technical, communication, critical thinking, and problem-solving areas.

2. Provide opportunities for up skilling and retooling for teachers to stay abreast of advancements in their respective fields and better support students' skill development.

Teachers:

3. Actively participate in professional development workshops and training sessions to enhance teaching techniques that promote skill development in students.
4. Stay updated on industry trends and advancements relevant to the subjects they teach, integrating real-world examples and case studies into the curriculum.

Future Researchers:

5. Conduct longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact of diploma programs on students' skill development and career outcomes.
6. Investigate the effectiveness of professional development workshops and training sessions for teachers in enhancing students' skill development outcomes and overall learning experience.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher showed all the necessary ethical consideration on the entire duration of the study. Since humans were chosen as the study participants, confidentiality of information was observed. Ensuring the dignity and privacy of participants is also a must. Further, minimizing potential risk to the participants was observed.

The researcher followed the ethical protocols of Metro Dumaguete College. To ensure that the research topic was evidently sound significant and ethically correct, consultation was pursued. Moreover, the participants signed a consent form along with the full understanding of the risk and benefits of the study being conducted.

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